

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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THE ROLE AND MAIN TYPES OF AGRICULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: this article describes the role of agricultural tourism in Uzbekistan and its main types. Available agricultural tourism spots had the opportunity to carry out different activities together with areas are visited by tourists. In this article, development of agrotourism and its cultural and spiritual significance have been discussed.

Key words: tourism, ecotourism, gastronomic tourism, horticulture tourism, handicraft tourism, pottery, wood-carving, bird-watching.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligi turizmining o'rni va uning asosiy turlari yoritilgan. Mavjud qishloq xo'jaligi sayyohlik joylari sayyohlar tashrif buyuradigan hududlar bilan birgalikda turli tadbirlarni amalga oshirish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ldi. Ushbu maqolada agroturizmni rivojlantirish va uning madaniy va ma'naviy ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, ekoturizm, gastronomik turizm, bog'dorchilik turizmi, hunarmandchilik turizmi, kulolchilik, yog'och o'ymakorligi, qushlarni kuzatish.

Аннотация: в статье описывается роль агротуризма в Узбекистане и его основные виды. Доступные места агротуризма имели возможность осуществлять различные виды деятельности вместе с территориями, посещаемыми туристами. В статье обсуждается развитие агротуризма и его культурное и духовное значение.

Ключевые слова: туризм, экотуризм, гастрономический туризм, садоводческий туризм, ремесленный туризм, гончарное дело, резьба по дереву, наблюдение за птицами.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, tourism is considered one of the fastest growing industries in the world. There are many opportunities for the development of each branch of tourism by our President, and at the same time, many important decisions about tourism have been made. In July 28, 1992 "Uzbekturizm" National Company was established in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This company was organized on the basis of the Republic of Uzbekistan Council of the Federation of Trade Unions, "Inturtaj" joint venture, "Sayyoh-Intur" the republic's economic association and former "Goscominturist" enterprises. "Uzbekturizm" National Company has been performed a certain amount of work to restoration of national and international tourism, strengthening and expansion of the material, technical and regulatory base, new development of tourism routes, updating of excursion topics, improvement of existing tourism base and campsites and creation of new ones, provision of additional services on increasing its size during several years. Level of development of tourism - is one of the descriptive parameters socio-economic development of the country, its regions and the well-being of the population. Innovation plays an especially important role in the field of tourism.

World practice shows that tourism comes second after oil and gas extraction. Tourism in many countries is the most important area of economic activity for national economies. Also, tourism is an information-rich field, in which collection of information, transmission, analysis and storage of information, it should be noted that it plays an important role in decision-making at all levels.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Tourism changes in the field are one of the strategic directions of the development of the national economy and it can ensure rapid development of regions. There are several main varieties of agricultural tourism.

Ecotourism involves visiting unspoiled natural areas. This helps to protect the environment and improve the welfare of the local population. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's Decree No. PF-4861 of December 2, 2016 "Measures to ensure rapid development of tourism industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan" created a radical turn in the development of tourism, a new stage, conditions for promising reforms in tourism in our country.

The term **agritourism** is used to describe nearly any activity in which a visitor to the farm or other agricultural setting contemplates the farm landscape or participates in an agricultural process for recreation or leisure purposes. This provides an opportunity for travelers experiencing village life, tasting local food and different farming to get acquainted with the tasks. Some types of agritourism are called direct market agritourism, experience and education. Agricultural tourism (agritourism) in Uzbekistan has been developing rapidly in recent years and serves to promote tourism in rural areas and support the local economy. The country's natural conditions, rich agricultural resources and rural culture create ample opportunities for agricultural tourism.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The main types of agricultural tourism in Uzbekistan:

Farm and horticulture tourism. Tourists visit vineyards, orchards, cotton fields and vegetable farms. Participants in fruit harvesting (cherries, grapes, peaches, pomegranates, melons, etc.) are familiarity with organic farming and the cultivation of environmentally friendly products.

Livestock and beekeeping tourism. Visitors can see and participate in the process of raising cows, sheep, goats, horses and camels in rural areas. They get to know the process of collecting honey in beekeeping farms and the beneficial properties of natural honey.

Gastronomic tourism. Master classes are held by cooking and tasting food Uzbek national dishes (pilaf, somsa, shashlik, tandir bread, etc.) from farm products. Tourists visit as guests in a traditional kitchen in the village for tasting national drinks (shubat, qimiz).

Recreation in nature. Tourists do several activities such as hiking in mountainous areas, bird watching, fishing in rivers and lakes.

Cultural and handicraft tourism. Visit to handicraft centers in Uzbek villages (Margilan - silk making, Rishton - pottery, Khiva - wood carving) gives a new experience. People get to know the process of weaving national clothes and carpets. Participants see in village holidays and festivals (Navroz, harvest festival, etc.). Popular rural tourism destinations in Uzbekistan are Samarkand region (horticulture, viticulture, ecotourism).

Advantages of agricultural tourism

It creates an additional source of income for local residents.

It promotes an ecologically clean and a healthy lifestyle.

It allows tourists to get to know the traditional culture and nature of Uzbekistan.

Agrotourism has begun to develop more actively and spread to other countries, thereby solving various problems:

❖ Protection of the environment, nature and ecology

❖ Preservation of the traditions of rural areas

❖ Directing tourists to a healthy lifestyle

❖ Economic effect, an increase in the spheres of activity

CONCLUSION

Agrotourism refers to an additional source of income for rural areas with a declining standard of living, agrotourism can increase the competitiveness of a small farmer. Agrotourism is one of the main economic instruments and promising areas for the development of rural areas. The development of agricultural tourism in Uzbekistan makes it possible to raise the standard of living of the local population and turn rural areas into attractive tourist destinations. Besides that, agricultural tourism creates workplace and provides a job for local people in touristic areas. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are problems of lack of qualified personnel, lack of knowledge about foreign experience and own recreational resources in rural areas. The effective development of agrotourism requires state support and a deep study of foreign experience.

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